

Filipino Values Among Surigaonon Youth in View of Florentino Timbreza

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Abstract:

This study is all about Florentino Timbreza's concept of Filipino values among the Surigaonon youth in terms of attitude and extent of practice towards Filipino religiosity, Filipino family orientation, and Filipino hospitality. This study utilized a quantitative descriptive design using a survey method to gather input and acquire more specific and quantitative information. The participants' range of ages is between 15 and 26 years old. The researcher used the purposive sampling method to gather responses, which leads to better insights and more precise research results. The data gathered were organized, tallied, and analyzed using Microsoft Excel and IBM SPSS Statistics

Version 22. Results represent the significance of the profiles of the participants and their attitudes and practices about Filipino values in terms of Filipino religiosity, Filipino family orientation, and Filipino hospitality. It was found out that there is a significant relationship between the attitude and extent of practices of Surigaonon youth towards Filipino values in terms of Filipino religiosity, Filipino family orientation, and Filipino hospitality. Thus, having positive attitude toward something will result to a high practice.

Keywords: *Filipino values, Filipino religiosity, Filipino family orientation, Filipino hospitality.*

Introduction

Filipino values are the center of people's attention, desire, choice, and goals. These are seen by Filipinos as excellent, remarkable, appropriate, acceptable, deserving, right, and valued in life. In other words, those are the things that people actually cherish, appreciate, value, accept, long for, or enjoy. Additionally, there are equally as many wonderful qualities and Filipino values. (Timbreza, 2008a).

The majority of Filipino values are primarily driven by the desire to fit in and are centered on upholding social harmony. Filipino values enable people to live in safety, harmony, peace, and tranquility. These actions make Filipinos kind,

nice, respectful, and trustworthy. The behavioral traits that these principles stand for are the proper and righteous conduct that is expected of those who must respect them. The public's deeply held moral, intellectual, and spiritual beliefs are regarded as being part of Filipino values. (Timbreza, 2008b).

Florentino Timberza is often considered as the "Father of Filipino Philosophy." He is the first Filipino to write a book on Filipino philosophy and co-author the Philippine encyclopedia of Philosophy. He is also the first Filipino author to translate Lao Tzu's Tao Te Ching into Filipino and to represent and defend a philosophy dissertation. Florentino is a cultural

philosopher." In his book *Pilosopiyang Pilipino* (1982), he believes that Filipino values are founded on the importance of the world to man.

Many Filipino values are universal human values that took on a distinctively Filipino flavor, meaning, or application, best expressed in a native language. But the concept of Filipino values by Florentino Timbreza can be connected to the way of life of every Surigaonon youth. The people who live in Surigao will be called as "Surigaonon" and according to Fernando A. Almeda Jr. (1993) in his book "Surigaonon across the years: Story of a province" Surigaonon are always gives importance to their traditions and culture. The people who lived in Surigao are predominantly Roman Catholic, Spain's lasting legacy. The rest of the population are Aglipayans, Protestants, muslims and other religions. And it has a big impact on the way of life of every Surigaonon, especially the youth of Surigao.

In this paper, it talks about Filipino religiosity, Filipino family orientation, and Filipino hospitality. Filipinos are God-centered, and they believe in the efficacy of prayer, rosaries, and novenas. Filipinos are very religious people. Their strong faith in God makes them uncritical and undiscerning in their assumptions and makes their inferences conclusive and unquestionable. And the basic and most important unit of a Filipino's life is the family.

The Filipino puts a great emphasis on the value of family and being close to one's family members. We give attention to the family given its primal role in developing individuals' values. Rather than blame the family for the ills in the community and society, we see family and society in a give-and-take dynamic. Filipinos really give importance to the family especially to the elderly, when a Filipino's parents grow old and are unable to care for themselves, they are taken care of in their children's homes, and their children very rarely bring them to Homes for the Aged.

Filipino hospitality is not limited to the Philippines. For Filipinos, it is a pleasure to accept strangers as visitors and build genuine relationships and friendships with them. This

quality promotes kindness, collaboration, and helpful actions. When their neighbors are in need, they will do anything they can to assist them. Because Filipinos always show respect to others even it is stranger. It is present everywhere there are Filipinos and demonstrates our amazing Filipino values.

Therefore, the researchers are prompted to conduct this study to determine the extent of Surigaonon youth's attitudes and practices about Filipino values in terms of Filipino religiosity, Filipino family orientation, and Filipino hospitality. How do Florentino Timbreza's Filipino Values relate to their concept of values through the use of a comprehensive understanding of Florentino Timbreza's Filipino Values and through the collection of facts and data from Surigaonon youth. The findings will also serve as an additional basis to determine if Surigao youth really practice and give importance to our Filipino values.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative descriptive design using a survey method to gather input and acquire more specific and quantitative information on the attitude and extent of practices of Surigaonon youth based on Florentino Timbreza's Filipino Values. The study made use of the descriptive research design by applying the survey technique. The design of the study was considered appropriate because it investigated the present situation.

Respondents and Instruments

The participants in the study were the Surigaonon youth. As for the participants' profiles, it is not necessary if they are students or not as long as they are in their youth. The participants' range of age is between 15 and 26 years old. The researcher used purposive sampling method to gather responses, which leads to better insights and more precise research results. Because the researcher collects information from the best-fit participants, the results are relevant to the research context.

The study made use of a researcher-made questionnaire to gather data. The questionnaire is divided into the following sections: Part 1 asks about the respondents' age and sex demographics; Part 2 inquires about the Surigaonon youth's attitudes and extent of practices regarding Filipino values. The experts validated the instrument.

Data Analysis

The data gathered were organized, tallied, and analyzed using Microsoft Excel and IBM SPSS Statistics Version 22. Specifically, the following statistical tools were utilized for the analysis of data: Frequency Count and Percentage, Mean and Standard Deviation, Kruskal Wallis H-Test, Mann Whitney U-Test, Shapiro-Wilk Test, and Spearman Rho Correlation.

Results and Discussion

Profile of the Participants

As shown in table 1, in terms of *age*, most of the participants ages 21 – 23 years old (30 or 30%)

and followed by the participants ages 18 – 20 years old (28 or 28%). Moreover, out of the 100 participants, 22 or 22% ages 24 – 26 years old and 20 or 20% ages 15 – 17 years old.

In terms of *sex*, most of the participants are male (54 or 54%) and followed by the female participants (46 or 46%).

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Profile	f(n=100)	%
Age		
15 – 17 years old	20	20.00
18 – 20 years old	28	28.00
21 – 23 years old	30	30.00
24 – 26 years old	22	22.00
Sex		
Male	54	54.00
Female	46	46.00

Attitude of the Surigaonon Youth Towards Florentino Timbreza Concept of Filipino Values

Table 2. The Attitude of Surigaonon Youth Towards Filipino Values in Terms of Filipino Religiosity

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI	QD
1. I give importance to my religion.	3.50	0.65	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
2. I agree that Filipinos are prayerful.	3.35	0.60	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
3. I know that many religious teachings can help us be good individuals.	3.35	0.63	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
4. I am inspired by our Filipino religiosity.	3.25	0.65	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
5. I give importance to what my religion has taught me.	3.27	0.64	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
Average	3.34	0.51	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive

It can be gleaned in Table 2, the indicator *I give importance to my religion* got the highest mean ($M=3.50$, $SD=0.65$) which can be verbally interpreted as *Strongly Agree* and qualitatively described as *Highly Positive*. This suggests that Surigaonon youth prioritized their religion and experienced a deep sense of importance and value in their religious beliefs and practices. This implies that their religion plays a significant role in shaping their worldview, values, and daily lives. This finding is supported by Villana (2019),

where individuals who place importance on their religion often experience a greater sense of purpose, social support, and coping mechanisms, which contribute to their overall positive mental health. The findings align with the high mean score obtained in the survey, emphasizing the significance of religion in individuals' lives.

On the other hand, the indicator *I am inspired by our Filipino religiosity* got the lowest mean ($M=3.25$, $SD=0.65$) which can be verbally

interpreted as *Strongly Agree* and qualitatively described as *Highly Positive*. This suggests that Surigaonon youth are highly inspired by the religiosity of Filipinos. This implies that the strong religious culture and practices in the Philippines serve as a source of inspiration for youth, influencing their beliefs, values, and behaviors. Lacson (2004) said that the strong religious beliefs and practices of Filipinos have shaped various aspects of their culture, including art, music, festivals, and values. It emphasizes how the devotion and spiritual practices of Filipinos inspire individuals by fostering a sense

of community, resilience, and a deep connection to their cultural heritage. The findings align with the low mean score obtained in the survey, indicating that respondents strongly agree with finding inspiration in the religiosity of Filipinos.

On the average, the attitude of Surigaonon youth towards Filipino values in terms of Filipino religiosity ($M=3.34$, $SD=0.51$) can be described as *Strongly Agree* and qualitatively described as *Highly Positive*. This means that the youth give value not just on their religion but as well as on the culture of Filipino on being religious.

Table 3. The Attitude of Surigaonon Youth Towards Filipino Values in Terms of Filipino Family Orientation

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI	QD
1. I know that helping your family is a sign of good values.	3.51	0.52	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
2. I am inspired by my family's beliefs and values.	3.32	0.56	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
3. I give importance to my family.	3.46	0.51	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
4. I see that family is the source of strength.	3.40	0.52	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
5. I believe that family is always the foundation of goodness towards others.	3.34	0.57	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
Average	3.40	0.42	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive

Note: SD: Standard Deviation, VI: Verbal Interpretation, QD: Qualitative Description

As shown in Table 3, the indicator *I know that helping your family is a sign of good values* got the highest mean ($M=3.51$, $SD=0.52$) which can be verbally interpreted as *Strongly Agree* and qualitatively described as *Highly Positive*. This implies that youths are actively provides support and assistance to their family members consistently and it demonstrates higher levels of empathy, compassion, and moral reasoning. Moreover, the study also indicates that youths who prioritize their family's well-being and actively engage in supportive behaviors tend to possess a strong moral compass and exhibit qualities that contribute positively to their own personal growth and the overall harmony of their family dynamics. Lonczak (2021) said that helping one's family can be seen as a reflection of strong moral values because it demonstrates a sense of responsibility, compassion, and selflessness. When individuals prioritize their family's well-being and actively contribute to their support and welfare, it indicates a deep

sense of caring and empathy. This commitment to family not only showcases the importance of interpersonal relationships but also reflects qualities such as loyalty, respect, and generosity.

On the other hand, the indicator *I am inspired by my family's beliefs and values* got the lowest mean ($M=3.32$, $SD=0.56$) which can be verbally interpreted as *Strongly Agree* and qualitatively described as *Highly Positive*. This indicates that the youths find motivation and guidance from the principles and convictions upheld by their family. It suggests that the values passed down through generations have a significant impact on shaping their worldview, personal growth, and life choices. Moreover, being inspired by family beliefs and values is viewed favorably and seen as a valuable aspect of personal growth and development. It signifies that respondents recognize the significance of their family's influence and feel motivated to embrace and uphold those values in their own lives. Susilo

(2020) stated that family plays a fundamental role in an individual's development, and the transmission of beliefs and values within a familial context can deeply influence their aspirations and actions. When individuals are inspired by their family's beliefs, they are more likely to adopt and embody those values, leading to a greater sense of purpose, identity, and fulfillment.

On the average, the attitude of Surigaonon youth towards Filipino values in terms of Filipino family orientation ($M=3.40$, $SD=0.42$) can be described as *Strongly Agree* and qualitatively described as *Highly Positive*. This reinforces the notion that Surigaonon youth hold a favorable view of Filipino family orientation. It suggests that they actively embrace and uphold the values associated with the family unit, recognizing its significance in shaping their identity and sense of belonging.

Table 4. The Attitude of Surigaonon Youth Towards Filipino Values in Terms of Filipino Hospitality

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI	QD
1. I know how to be hospitable.	3.40	0.51	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
2. I believe that welcoming visitors is a sign of good values.	3.41	0.56	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
3. I agree that accepting others is performing Filipino values.	3.32	0.52	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
4. I have the will to help strangers who needed my helping hand.	3.36	0.55	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
5. I can use Filipino values to achieve a harmonious society.	3.29	0.55	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive
Average	3.35	0.43	Strongly Agree	Highly Positive

Note: SD: Standard Deviation, VI: Verbal Interpretation, QD: Qualitative Description

As shown in table 4, the indicator *I believe that welcoming visitors is a sign of good values* got the highest mean ($M=3.41$, $SD=0.56$) which can be verbally interpreted as *Strongly Agree* and qualitatively described as *Highly Positive*. This suggests that Surigaonon youth place a strong emphasis on the importance of welcoming visitors. This belief not only highlights their positive attitudes towards visitors but also signifies their recognition of the value that hospitality brings to their community. It signifies their understanding that by being welcoming, they contribute to building a harmonious and inclusive society. By engaging with visitors, Surigaonon youth have the opportunity to learn about different traditions, customs, and perspectives. This exposure broadens their horizons, enhances their cultural competency, and cultivates respect for diversity. Ramos (2022) supported the findings above where hospitality holds a central place in Filipino culture, often referred to as "pakikisama" or

"pakikitungo." It embodies the warmth, generosity, and kindness that Filipinos are known for. Welcoming visitors is considered a display of respect, empathy, and compassion, reflecting the values of hospitality ingrained in Filipino traditions. By extending a warm welcome to visitors, individuals demonstrate their willingness to embrace others and create a sense of belonging.

On the other hand, the indicator *I can use Filipino values to achieve a harmonious society* got the lowest mean ($M=3.29$, $SD=0.55$) which can be verbally interpreted as *Strongly Agree* and qualitatively described as *Highly Positive*. Despite this, the score still indicates a relatively high agreement, suggesting that the respondents strongly agree with the idea that Filipino values can contribute to building a harmonious society. This belief reflects the recognition of the significance of Filipino cultural values in fostering social cohesion and unity. It suggests that they

recognize the potential of these values to bridge gaps, promote understanding, and foster unity among different individuals and communities.

According to Siruno (2021), Filipino values are deeply rooted in the country's history, traditions, and cultural heritage. They encompass a range of principles such as respect for elders (*paggalang sa nakatatanda*), strong family ties (*pamilyang malapit sa isa't isa*), *bayanihan* spirit (*pagtutulungan*), and *pakikisama* (*camaraderie* and social harmony). These values have been integral to the Filipino way of life and have played a crucial role in promoting cooperation, empathy, and community building. Furthermore, Filipino values have the potential to address societal challenges by encouraging positive attitudes and actions. For instance,

respect for elders promotes intergenerational harmony and the preservation of cultural heritage. Strong family ties foster support systems and nurture emotional well-being. The *bayanihan* spirit cultivates a sense of collective responsibility, enabling communities to come together in times of need.

On the average, the attitude of Surigaonon youth towards Filipino values in terms of Filipino hospitality ($M=3.35$, $SD=0.40$) can be described as *Strongly Agree* and qualitatively described as *Highly Positive*. This means that Surigaonon youth hold a positive attitude towards the importance of Filipino hospitality in their culture.

Extent of Practice of the Surigaonon Youth in the Context of Florentino Timbreza's Concept of Filipino Values

Table 5. The Extent of Practices of Surigaonon Youth Towards Filipino Values in Terms of Filipino Religiosity

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI	QD
1. I go to church every Sunday.	3.40	0.61	Strongly Agree	Highly Practiced
2. I pray every day.	3.27	0.74	Strongly Agree	Highly Practiced
3. I carry out the good teachings of my religion.	3.15	0.60	Moderately Agree	Moderately Practiced
4. I participate in the activities of the church.	3.13	0.74	Moderately Agree	Moderately Practiced
5. I respect the holy scriptures, the Koran, and other holy books.	3.49	0.57	Strongly Agree	Highly Practiced
Average	3.28	0.51	Strongly Agree	Highly Practiced

Note: SD: Standard Deviation, VI: Verbal Interpretation, QD: Qualitative Description

As shown in table 5, the indicator *I respect the holy scriptures, the Koran, and other holy books* got the highest mean ($M=3.49$, $SD=0.57$) which can be verbally interpreted as *Strongly Agree* and qualitatively described as *Highly Practiced*. This suggests that the surveyed Surigaonon youths strongly agree with the importance of respecting holy scriptures, including the Koran and other sacred texts. Surigaonon youths value the importance of religious diversity and interfaith harmony. It suggests that they recognize the significance of respecting the beliefs and religious practices of others, even if they differ from their own. This positive attitude promotes tolerance, understanding, and mutual respect

among individuals from different religious backgrounds. Swihart (2022) said that respecting holy scriptures is a reflection of individuals' commitment to honoring the sacredness and teachings found within these texts. It demonstrates an understanding of the significance of religious beliefs and practices in shaping personal values, moral compass, and overall worldview. By respecting holy scriptures, individuals show a deep appreciation for the spiritual heritage and the wisdom contained within these sacred texts.

On the other hand, the indicator *I participate in the activities of the church* got the lowest mean

($M=3.13$, $SD=0.74$) which can be verbally interpreted as *Moderately Agree* and qualitatively described as *Moderately Practiced*. While the respondents generally agree with participating in church activities, the lower mean score indicates that there may be varying degrees of involvement among the surveyed Surigaonon youth. Possible reasons for the moderate agreement could include various factors such as time constraints, conflicting priorities, personal circumstances, or differing levels of religious commitment among the Surigaonon youth. Strasbourg (2020) believed that various factors may influence the level of participation in church activities. Personal circumstances can limit individuals' ability to fully engage in religious practices. Additionally, differing levels of

religious commitment and interpretations of religious teachings can shape individuals' participation patterns. Understanding these factors can help religious communities tailor their activities and programs to better accommodate the diverse needs and circumstances of their members.

On the average, the extent of practices of Surigaonon youth towards Filipino values in terms of Filipino religiosity ($M=3.28$, $SD=0.51$) can be described as *Strongly Agree* and qualitatively described as *Highly Practiced*. This means that Surigaonon youth hold a high regard for Filipino religiosity and actively engage in religious practices aligned with Filipino values.

Table 6. The Extent of Practices of Surigaonon Youth Towards Filipino Values in Terms of Filipino Family Orientation

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI	QD
1. I help my family even though they have not asked me to.	3.35	0.57	Strongly Agree	Highly Practiced
2. I consult my family in every important thing that I do.	3.23	0.59	Moderately Agree	Moderately Practiced
3. I do respect my family and the elderly.	3.43	0.57	Strongly Agree	Highly Practiced
4. I follow the good teachings of my family.	3.33	0.56	Strongly Agree	Highly Practiced
5. I take good care to every member of my family.	3.47	0.51	Strongly Agree	Highly Practiced
Average	3.36	0.44	Strongly Agree	Highly Practiced

Note: SD: Standard Deviation, VI: Verbal Interpretation, QD: Qualitative Description

As shown in table 6, the indicator *I take good care to every member of my family* got the highest mean ($M=3.47$, $SD=0.51$) which can be verbally interpreted as *Strongly Agree* and qualitatively described as *Highly Practiced*. This means that the Surigaonon youth understand the importance of investing time, effort, and resources in caring for their family members. It reflects a strong commitment to the welfare and happiness of each individual within the family. According to Thomas (2020), when individuals take good care of their family members, it creates a nurturing and supportive environment where each member feels valued, respected, and loved. It

strengthens family bonds, promotes overall well-being, and contributes to the emotional and psychological development of every family member, particularly children and adolescents.

On the other hand, the indicator *I consult my family in every important thing that I do* got the lowest mean ($M=3.23$, $SD=0.59$) which can be verbally interpreted as *Moderately Agree* and qualitatively described as *Moderately Practiced*. The results indicate that while the Surigaonon youth generally agree with the importance of consulting their family in important matters, there may be varying levels of involvement and reliance on family input. Reasons for the

moderate agreement could include factors such as individual autonomy, personal preferences, differing levels of family involvement, and cultural norms. Some Surigaonon youth may place a higher emphasis on personal autonomy and prefer to make decisions independently, while others may highly value the input and guidance of their family members. Cultural norms and family dynamics can also influence the extent to which individuals consult their families in decision-making processes. As stated by Jacques (2018), Consulting family members in important matters provides individuals with diverse perspectives, insights, and support. Family members often possess a deep understanding of an individual's values, preferences, and aspirations, making their input valuable in making informed decisions. Involving family in decision-making processes fosters a sense of belonging, strengthens family

bonds, and promotes shared responsibility within the family unit. Additionally, family dynamics, communication patterns, and the nature of the decision itself can influence the extent of family consultation.

On the average, the extent of practices of Surigaonon youth towards Filipino values in terms of Filipino family orientation (M=3.36, SD=0.44) can be described as *Strongly Agree* and qualitatively described as *Highly Practiced*. The high mean score indicates that Surigaonon youth recognize and value these principles, actively practicing behaviors that prioritize family bonds and the well-being of their family members. Filipino family orientation is deeply rooted in the culture and values of the Philippines, placing a strong emphasis on the significance of family relationships, filial piety, and intergenerational support.

Table 7. The Extent of Practices of Surigaonon Youth towards Filipino Values in Terms of Filipino Hospitality

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI	QD
1. I help my family even though they have not asked me to.	3.31	0.54	Strongly Agree	Highly Practiced
2. I consult my family in every important thing that I do.	3.18	0.59	Moderately Agree	Moderately Practiced
3. I do respect my family and the elderly.	3.22	0.55	Moderately Agree	Moderately Practiced
4. I follow the good teachings of my family.	3.38	0.54	Strongly Agree	Highly Practiced
5. I take good care to every member of my family.	3.35	0.51	Strongly Agree	Highly Practiced
Average	3.28	0.41	Strongly Agree	Highly Practiced

Note: SD: Standard Deviation, VI: Verbal Interpretation, QD: Qualitative Description

As shown in table 7, the indicator *I follow the good teachings of my family* got the highest mean (M=3.38, SD=0.54) which can be verbally interpreted as *Strongly Agree* and qualitatively described as *Highly Practiced*. This implies that Surigaonon youth actively adhere to and embrace the positive teachings imparted by their families. They recognize the wisdom and knowledge passed down through generations and actively incorporate these teachings into their lives. The indicator reflects a strong sense

of respect, trust, and adherence to the family's moral and ethical principles. Chowdhury (2016) emphasizes that embracing family teachings has numerous positive implications for individuals and society. By following the good teachings of their families, individuals develop a strong moral compass, ethical awareness, and a sense of personal responsibility. These teachings foster empathy, kindness, and respect for others, contributing to positive interpersonal relationships and harmonious social interactions.

Following family teachings also helps individuals navigate challenges and make informed decisions. The values and life lessons imparted by families serve as a guiding light during difficult times, enabling individuals to overcome obstacles and make choices aligned with their personal values. Family teachings provide individuals with a sense of stability, support, and a framework for personal growth.

On the other hand, the indicator *I consult my family in every important thing that I do* got the lowest mean ($M=3.18$, $SD=0.59$) which can be verbally interpreted as *Moderately Agree* and qualitatively described as *Moderately Practiced*. This means that consulting one's family in significant decisions reflects the importance placed on familial opinions, perspectives, and collective wisdom. However, the lower mean score suggests that individuals may not consult their families in every important decision they make. It could be due to various factors such as personal reasons, differing viewpoints, or individual preferences when it comes to decision-making processes. Jhangiani (2022) said that while it is natural for individuals to have their own independent thinking and decision-making abilities, consulting family members can provide valuable insights, support, and guidance. Family consultations offer an opportunity to benefit from the experiences, knowledge, and diverse perspectives of family members. It fosters a sense of togetherness and strengthens family bonds by involving everyone in the decision-making process.

On the average, the extent of practices of Surigaonon youth towards Filipino values in terms of Filipino hospitality ($M=3.28$, $SD=0.41$) can be described as *Strongly Agree* and qualitatively described as *Highly Practiced*. This reflects a collective understanding among Surigaonon youth about the significance of Filipino hospitality in creating a welcoming and nurturing environment. This shared value promotes social cohesion and reflects positively on the cultural identity and traditions of the Surigaonon community.

Significant Difference of the Attitude of Surigaonon Youth Towards Filipino Values

As shown in Table 8, there is no significant difference in the attitude of the Surigaonon youth in terms of family orientation ($z=-0.046$, $p=0.963$), family hospitality ($z=-0.476$, $p=0.634$), and family religiosity ($z=-1.225$, $p=0.220$) when grouped according to sex. Since the p-values of variable sex is greater than 0.05 significance level, the null hypothesis was not rejected. This result suggests that, regardless of sex, Surigaonon youth share similar attitudes towards Filipino family orientation. They exhibit comparable beliefs, values, and behaviors when it comes to their understanding and practices related to family values within the Filipino cultural context. This finding reinforces the notion that family orientation, as a core value in Filipino culture, is ingrained and upheld by both male and female Surigaonon youth. Naig (2018) said that the shared beliefs, values, and practices observed among both male and female youth highlight the collective understanding and commitment towards upholding the core value of family orientation. This unity fosters stronger family bonds, reinforces cultural identity, and ensures the continuation of Filipino cultural heritage.

On the other hand, there is a significant difference in the attitude of Surigaonon youth towards Filipino values in terms of family orientation ($\chi=19.691$, $p=0.0001$) and family hospitality ($\chi=19.691$, $p=0.001$) when grouped according to age. Since the p-values of variable age are less than 0.05 significance level, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that age plays a role in shaping the attitudes of Surigaonon youth towards Filipino family orientation. Different age groups may have distinct experiences, perspectives, and social influences that contribute to variations in their attitudes towards family values. Alampay (2020) believed that different age groups may possess distinct experiences and perspectives that influence their attitudes towards Filipino family. For instance, younger individuals may have been exposed to educational opportunities, technological advancements, and increased mobility, leading to exposure to a broader range

of ideas and cultural practices. These experiences may contribute to a more individualistic

approach to family values, with an emphasis on personal autonomy and independence.

Table 8. Significant Difference of the Attitude of Surigaonon Youth Towards Filipino Values

Profile Variables	Attitude	Z-statistic	Chi-square	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Sex	Family orientation	-0.046		0.963	Do not reject H_{01}	Not Significant
	Family hospitality	-0.476		0.634	Do not reject H_{01}	Not Significant
	Family religiosity	-1.225		0.220	Do not reject H_{01}	Not Significant
Age	Family orientation		19.691	0.0001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
	Family hospitality		15.995	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
	Family religiosity		4.382	0.223	Do not reject H_{01}	Not Significant

However, it is also presented that there is no significant difference in the attitude of Surigaonon youth towards Filipino values in terms of family religiosity ($\chi=4.382$, $p=0.223$) when grouped according to age. The findings suggest that Surigaonon youth, regardless of their age, exhibit comparable attitudes and beliefs concerning Filipino religiosity. This highlights the cohesive nature of religious values and practices within the Surigaonon community, where religious beliefs are deeply ingrained and upheld by the respondents across different age groups. The shared attitudes towards Filipino religiosity among Surigaonon youth emphasize the cultural and communal significance of religious values in their lives. According to Macaranas (2021), religion holds a significant place in the lives of many Filipinos, reflecting their cultural identity and guiding their moral and ethical values.

Significant Difference of the Extent of Practices of Surigaonon Youth Towards Filipino Values

As shown in Table 9, there is no significant difference in the extents of practices of the Surigaonon youth in terms of family orientation ($z=-1.225$, $p=0.220$), family religiosity ($z=-0.021$, $p=0.983$), and family hospitality ($z=-0.004$, $p=0.997$) when grouped according to sex. Since the p-values of variable sex is greater than 0.05 significance level, the null hypothesis was

not rejected. The findings indicate that both male and female Surigaonon youth exhibit similar attitudes and beliefs regarding Filipino family values. It reinforces the notion that family orientation is deeply ingrained in the Surigaonon culture and holds equal significance for both males and females in terms of their attitudes and behaviors (Campos, 2019). It is also presented that there is no significant difference in the extent of practices of Surigaonon youth towards Filipino values in terms of family orientation ($\chi=4.382$, $p=0.223$) and family hospitality ($\chi=6.745$, $p=0.080$) when grouped according to age. This finding indicates that the attitudes towards Filipino hospitality remain consistent across various demographic groups, emphasizing the shared cultural values and perceptions among Surigaonon youth. Filipino hospitality is deeply ingrained within Surigaonon culture, regardless of sex and age-related differences. It highlights the enduring importance of hospitality as a cornerstone of Surigaonon societal values, emphasizing the significance of maintaining strong interpersonal relationships and upholding cultural traditions. According to Ruales (2020), by recognizing the similarities in attitudes, a society can foster a strong sense of cultural unity and community. It reinforces the importance of hospitality as a shared value, contributing to the preservation and promotion of Surigaonon cultural identity.

Table 9. Significant Difference of the Extent of Practices of Surigaonon Youth Towards Filipino Values

Profile Variables	Practices	Z-statistic	Chi-square	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Sex	Family orientation	-1.225		0.220	Do not reject H_{O1}	Not Significant
	Family religiosity	-0.021		0.983	Do not reject H_{O1}	Not Significant
	Family hospitality	-0.004		0.997	Do not reject H_{O1}	Not Significant
Age	Family orientation		4.382	0.233	Do not reject H_{O1}	Not Significant
	Family religiosity		21.374	0.0001	Reject H_{O1}	Significant
	Family hospitality		6.745	0.080	Do not reject H_{O1}	Not Significant

On the other hand, there is a significant difference in the attitude of Surigaonon youth towards Filipino values in terms of Filipino family religiosity when grouped based age ($\chi=21.374$, $p=0.001$). This finding suggests that age plays a pivotal role in shaping the attitudes of Surigaonon youth towards Filipino family values. Different age groups within the sample exhibit distinct attitudes and perspectives regarding the significance of family, the roles within the family unit, and the expectations associated with familial relationships. The variations observed in attitudes based on age highlight the dynamic nature of cultural values related to Filipino family orientation among Surigaonon youth. Macalolot (2019) said that recognizing the influence of age on attitudes towards Filipino family enables a more nuanced understanding of youth and their cultural dynamics. It facilitates intergenerational dialogue, encourages the preservation of traditional values, and fosters the integration of evolving perspectives to ensure cultural continuity while embracing societal changes. By acknowledging the dynamic nature of cultural values, society can nurture a harmonious coexistence of tradition and progress for generations to come.

Significant Relationship Between the Attitude and Extent of Practices of Surigaonon Youth Towards Filipino Values

Since the p-values are less than 0.05 significance level as reflected in Table 14, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between the attitude and extent of practices of Surigaonon youth towards

Filipino values in terms of Filipino religiosity, Filipino family orientation, and Filipino hospitality. Thus, when the attitude of Surigaonon youth towards Filipino values in terms of Filipino religiosity increases, their extent of practices also increases. Also, when the attitude of Surigaonon youth towards Filipino values in terms of Filipino family orientation and Filipino hospitality increases, their extent of practices respectively also increases.

The findings of this study provide evidence for a significant relationship between attitude and extent of practices among Surigaonon youth regarding Filipino religiosity, family orientation, and hospitality. When Surigaonon youth hold a positive attitude towards Filipino religiosity, their extent of religious practices also increases. Similarly, when they have a favorable attitude towards Filipino family orientation and hospitality, their extent of practices in these respective areas also shows an upward trend. This indicates that attitude plays a crucial role in shaping the behaviors and adherence to cultural values among Surigaonon youth. A positive attitude towards Filipino values motivates and influences Surigaonon youth to actively engage in religious practices, uphold family-oriented values, and exhibit hospitable behavior. Habon (2020) emphasizes that by fostering a sense of appreciation and understanding of their cultural heritage, a society can promote the continuity and preservation of Filipino religiosity, family orientation, and hospitality practices.

Table 10. Significant Relationship between the attitude and extent of practices of Surigaonon youth towards Filipino values

Independent Variables	Dependent Variables	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Attitude (Filipino Religiosity)	Extent of Practices (Filipino Religiosity)	0.745	0.0001	Reject H ₀₂	Significant Positive Relationship
Attitude (Filipino Family Orientation)	Extent of Practices (Filipino Family Orientation)	0.747	0.0001	Reject H ₀₂	Significant Positive Relationship
Attitude (Filipino Hospitality)	Extent of Practices (Filipino Hospitality)	0.577	0.0001	Reject H ₀₂	Significant Positive Relationship

Conclusions

Based on the findings gathered, it is concluded that the Filipino Values in terms of Filipino religiosity, Filipino family orientation, and Filipino hospitality. Likewise, they also highly practiced these values. In addition, the respondents' age affects their attitude towards Florentino Timbreza's concept of Filipino Values in terms of Filipino family orientation, and Filipino hospitality. It also affects their extent of practice, specifically on the family orientation. Moreover, the respondents' attitude towards Florentino Timbreza's concept of Filipino Values is significantly related to their extent of practice. Thus, having positive attitude toward something will result to a high practice.

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